

Effectiveness and feasibility of Activity Coach+; a physical activity intervention in hard-to-reach physically disabled people

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Abstract PURPOSE: Physically disabled participate less in physical activity (PA) compared to healthy people. Existing PA interventions are mainly performed in rehabilitation-, school- or primary healthcare settings, limiting their reach. Systematic development applying Intervention Mapping resulted in the community-based intervention Activity Coach+, aiming to stimulate both organized and non-organized PA in hard-to-reach physically disabled people. The purpose of this study was to test effectiveness and feasibility of Activity Coach+. METHODS: Activity Coach+ was implemented in community, and evaluated using a longitudinal study including measurements at baseline, and after 2, 4, 6 and 12 months. PA behavior was measured using the Activ8 accelerometer and the adapted SQUASH questionnaire. Body mass index (BMI), waist circumference, systolic blood pressure, hand grip force, 10 meter walk test, 6 minute walk test and Berg Balance Scale were measured to assess health changes. Bio psychosocial health was assessed using the RAND-36, Exercise Self-Efficacy Scale, Fatigue Severity Scale and IMPACT-S questionnaire. Data was analyzed using non-parametric Friedman tests. RESULTS: Currently, results of the first four months after implementation of Activity Coach+ are present. During the first four months, 29 hard-to-reach physically disabled people participated in Activity Coach+, of whom two dropped out. PA behavior did not change within the first four months. BMI ($p=.004$), 10 meter walk test ($p=.001$), 6 minute walk test ($p=.020$), dynamic balance ($p=.014$) and vitality (RAND-36) ($p=.049$) increased over time after implementation of Activity Coach+. A relevant trend was found for the increase of hand grip force ($p=.055$). CONCLUSION: Activity Coach+ was found feasible in a community setting. First indications for effectiveness of Activity Coach+ in hard-to-reach physically disabled people were provided. Long-term effectiveness of Activity Coach+ will be presented at the conference.

Keywords Physical activity, disability, health promotion

Introduction

Physical inactivity has a major burden on health, being the fourth leading cause of death worldwide. It is recently called pandemic (Andersen, Mota et al., 2016). Physically disabled people participate substantially less in physical activity (PA) compared to healthy people.

Existing interventions were mainly rehabilitation-, primary school- or primary healthcare based, what limits their reach (von Heijden, van den Dool et al. 2013). The existing Dutch intervention 'Activity Coach' (Dutch: Beweegcoach) was adapted into the new intervention 'Activity Coach+' to also reach the hard-to-reach population, by applying Intervention Mapping. The current study aimed to test feasibility and effectiveness of Activity Coach+ for stimulating PA in hard-to-reach physically disabled people.

Methods

Intervention

Within Activity Coach+, participants were recruited via a network of intermediate organizations, and through local media. Participants had a pre-intervention physiotherapeutic intake including history taking and physical assessment. An activity coach guided participants to participation in organized PA (by informing about local opportunities), non-organized PA (by connecting buddies) and PA during activities of daily living (by monitoring daily activity using an activity tracker). Counseling took place after 2, 4, 6 and 12 months (Krops, Dekker et al., 2018).

Participants

Participants of Activity Coach+ were physically disabled people, and were at least one year post-rehabilitation, or have not been treated by a rehabilitation center. Participants of Activity Coach+ were asked to voluntarily participate in research.

Data collection and analyses

Feasibility was measured as number of participants, number of dropouts and compliance with the protocol, which was reported by the activity coaches.

Effects of Activity Coach+ on PA behavior and health outcomes were determined in a one year prospective cohort study without a control group. Measurements were performed at baseline, and after 2, 4, 6, and 12 months. Measurements included:

- PA behavior; objective (Activ8; 2M Engineering) and self-reported (adapted SQUASH questionnaire)
- Biological health outcomes (body mass index (BMI), waist circumference, blood pressure)
- Functional outcomes (hand grip strength, 10m walk test, 6 minute walk test, and Berg Balance Scale)
- Psychosocial outcomes (RAND-36, Exercise Self-Efficacy Scale, and IMPACT-S questionnaire).

Because of non-normal distribution of the data, longitudinal progression of the outcome parameters over time was analyzed using non-parametric Friedman tests (SPSS 20.1).

Results

Within the first four months after implementation of Activity Coach+, 29 physically disabled people enrolled, of whom 21 participated in research. Participants (age 60.3 ± 13.1 y) suffered from various disabilities, amongst others brain injury, cardiopulmonary diseases and rheumatoid arthritis. Participants had been recruited via general practitioners ($n=6$), domestic care ($n=6$),

local newspapers ($n=5$), physiotherapists ($n=2$) and social work ($n=2$). All 21 participants underwent physiotherapeutic intake and intake with the activity coach. Counseling sessions at 2 and 4 months were adopted in respectively 20 and 19 participants, and the activity tracker was used by 18 participants.

PA behavior did not change significantly over time. Body mass index (BMI) ($\chi^2=11.217$ (2), $p=.004$), 10 meter walk test ($\chi^2=13.119$ (2), $p=.001$), 6 minute walk test ($\chi^2=7.860$ (2), $p=.020$), dynamic balance ($\chi^2=8.600$ (2), $p=.014$), and vitality (RAND-36) ($\chi^2=6.035$ (2), $p=.049$) significantly increased over time. Although not significant, a relevant trend was seen for the increase of hand grip force. For the other outcomes, no significant or relevant change over time was found.

Figure 1. Boxplots of outcomes that changed significantly over time after implementation of Activity Coach+. BMI = Body mass index, 10m WT = 10 meter walk test, 6min WT = 6 minute walk test; BBS = Berg Balance Scale; VT = vitality

Conclusion and discussion

The implementation of Activity Coach+ in a municipality setting was feasible. Daily PA behavior did not change during the first four months after implementation of Activity Coach+. BMI, walking ability, exercise capacity, dynamic balance and vitality increased during the first four months. The increase of BMI was not as desired, and is suggested to be explained by seasonal influences or increase of muscle mass. Although PA behavior did not change over time, the current study provides first indications for the effects of Activity Coach+ on health and functioning in hard-to-reach physically disabled people. Long-term effectiveness will be presented during the conference.

References

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